

BIM Automation for the Design of Building Services

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Abstract

BIM automation for design can contribute to the reducing of time and cost for Design. The proposed method automates design calculations and 3D drawing, saving up designer time for other important tasks. The main objective of this paper is automating the design in BIM to decrease the chance of clashes and increase the efficiency of design systems.

Whatever the scale of the project, mechanical, electrical, and plumbing system have a significant part in the cost and total duration of the project. This case study illustrates the current situation of the private project in Egypt, as well as the findings of the research, conducted in collaboration with one of the leading general contractors in “Slovenia” “Kliktor Kiling d.o.o”. The general contractor team has extensive BIM knowledge from previous projects. The case studies concentrated on specific sorts of automation design for MEP project construction.

This work intends to provide an overview of BIM automation strategies for building service design. The advantages and conclusions of this study may be summarized as total time savings, overall cost savings, and higher productivity.

Dissertation:

Link for full text

Presentation video:

https://youtu.be/mfBUXI_1sQ8

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